

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Report on the correlation between spray conditions and vitality of the biopesticidal microbes

SPOKE 6 - PRIMARY AGROINDUSTRY

Flagship Project VINO

DELIVERABLE D5.3

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this report we investigated the possible relationship between spray conditions and vitality of the biopesticidal microbes by measuring the vitality of entomopathogenic nematodes (EPN), Assessment of the pump effect on EPN vitality.

Report on the correlation between spray conditions and vitality of bio-pesticidal microbes

Set up of the most suitable method to measure the vitality of entomopathogenic nematodes (EPN), Assessment of the pump effect on EPN vitality

Set up of a reliable method to measure the vitality of Entomopathogenic Nematodes (EPN)

Trials were conducted using commercial formulations containing the most common EPNs: *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora*, *Steinernema carpocapsae*, and *Steinernema feltiae*. To adjust the methodology for the assessment of nematode viability, for each species 4 different types of counts were carried out. For the samples to be counted at the same time, 4 different mixtures were prepared under the same conditions and these mixtures were kept at different temperatures (10°C, 20°C, 30°C, 40°C) for 4.5 hours, sampling at time 0 and each 90 min (T0 → 0 min; T1 → 90 min; T2 → 180 min; T3 → 250 min, 4 samples/mixture). Of these 4 mixtures, each was evaluated in a different way (Table 1) according to the following protocol:

Procedure under stereomicroscope:

- Each sample was diluted 1/10 for evaluation.
- 50 µL of the dilution were used for examination under the microscope.
- For P2 and P3, another drop of 25 µL of the respective salt solutions was added to the drop.

Table 1. Test description

Test	Description
P1	Touching each nematode with a needle to check for movement.
P2	Add 25 µL of diluted salt (0.1 g/mL) and wait 7 minutes before counting the live nematodes.
P3	Add 25 µL of diluted salt (0.2 g/mL) and wait 7 minutes before counting live nematodes.
P4	Count the nematodes directly under the microscope.

At the end of the experiment, no significant difference was recorded between tests P2-P4, whereas test P1 showed higher EPN vitality for all the test duration with thermal conditions up to 30°C. Therefore, the following experiments were conducted using P1.

Assessment of the pump effect on EPN vitality

The objective of this activity was evaluating the effect of a diaphragm hydraulic pump on the viability of a bionsecticide based on *H. bacteriophora*.

Experimental design

Two quantitative factors were investigated:

- Number of passes of the mixture through diaphragm hydraulic pump in six levels: 0 (negative control), 1, 10, 20, 30 and 40.
- Working pressure of the pump in three levels: 0, 4 and 8 bar.

The measured response variable was the viability of *H. bacteriophora* individuals.

The assay was replicated 3 times in the same condition.

Test bench

To carry out the test, the following materials were used: a hydraulic diaphragm pump COMET APS 71 that ensure a flow rate of 71 L/min at 0 MPa, two tanks connected between each other and a pressure regulator (Figure 1). The assay consisted of propelling the mixture from tank 1 to the tank 2 by the pump. To control the number of passes through the pump, the stopcock between tanks was closed. When tank 1 was empty we considered that the whole amount of mixture went through the pump, so the pump was stopped, and this was counted as one pass. After that, the stopcock was opened to allow the mixture flow from tank 2 to tank 1 and start again the process. The performance of a whole pass took 1:04 minutes.

Figure 1. Test bench

Mixture preparation

The applied commercial formulation was Nemagreen® (Biogard) at a concentration of 5.67g/L. For each assay 50L of spray mixture were prepared. To prepare the mixture, first 20 L of water were put into the bottom tank. Then, in a separated container, 5 L of water were mixed with the total amount of formulation with a mechanical agitator until the mixture looked homogeneous. After that, this mixture was added to the tank. Then, to ensure no product remains in the container, additional 5 L of water were mixed and then put in the first tank. Finally, the first tank was filled up to 50 L.

Number of passages and temperature monitoring

The maximum number of passages to be applied (40) was calculated according to available literature to estimate the maximum number of times that the mixture could be recirculated through the pump during a real application in field conditions in a vineyard. For this the following parameters were considered: 44 minutes of spraying time, a sprayer with a tank capacity of 400L, a flow rate through the pump of 75 L/min, a flow rate through pump return, bypassed to the tank, of 66 L/min and a flow rate by nozzle of 9 L/min. During the trial the starting time (when the pump was activated) and the ending of each passage (when the pump was shut down) were recorded, and the number of passages was counted. The temperature was monitored using a datalogger (Delta OHM HD32.8). Three thermocouples were introduced

inside the mixture (nearby the pump suction) using a metal tube avoiding the thermocouple to touch the tank. The temperature of each passage was recorded.

Sampling and EPN viability evaluation

To take each sample, 50 mL of the mixture were harvested directly from the tank 2 when the mixture was falling to the tank 1. The samples were collected when tank 2 was half empty. The samples were examined immediately at the microscope to assess EPN viability using protocol P1.

The results showed no significant difference of EPN mortality after exposure to pump pressure of 0, 4, or 8 bar.